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NEWS

Visual Astronomy Display: February 2014

Katie Frey Updated on August 24, 2022 Leave a Comment

Visual Astronomy Display for February 2014

Highlights...

- Engineers and scientists at the Jet Propulsion Laboratory talk about the **amazing discoveries of Opportunity** which is still functioning on the surface of Mars a full ten years after it landed in 2004;
- A neat little video from MinutePhysics about **how the solar system has ended up relatively flat** even in a 3D universe;
- Hank from the SciShow rounds up some of the information we have learned since the **Chelyabinsk Meteor crashed to earth** one year ago;
- Japanese astronaut Koichi Wakata gives us a tour of his **International Space Station living quarters**; and
- An exploration of recently discovered **“Hot Jupiter” exoplanets**, showing us that these planets are weirder than anything astronomers have imagined.

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Bonus Videos...

- [Operating a Rover on Mars](#) discusses the challenges involved in the monumental task of keeping a vehicle running on different planet for 10 years.
- [How Spirit & Opportunity Affected Our Lives](#) is about how the twin rovers journey on Mars has affected their lives and careers of engineers and scientists at JPL.

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Katie Frey leads the development of the Unified Astronomy Thesaurus, a community supported linked data vocabulary for sorting, filtering, and exploring astronomical literature, data sets, images, etc.

About Katie Frey

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